

The application of higher oxygenated e-fuels (HOEF)/diesel blends in marine engine: A numerical analysis for the fishing vessel in Adriatic Sea

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Abstract

Fishing vessel propulsion systems are major maritime emission sources due to their reliance on compression ignition engines. This study evaluates engine performance and emissions using oxygenated e-fuel/diesel blends. Utilizing AVL Cruise™ M, a real-time simulation model was developed and validated against steady-state data and transient measurements from a trawler operating in the Adriatic Sea. Two synthetic e-fuels were analysed: HOEF I (C₅₋₁₃ alcohols) and HOEF II (C₁₀₋₂₂ ethers), blended with diesel at various volume ratios under steady-state and transient conditions. Despite lower carbon mass ratios in the e-fuels, CO₂ emissions remained largely unchanged. However, the study observed significant reductions in NO_x, CO, and SO₂, contrasted by an increase in soot emissions, particularly during transient operations. For a 50% HOEF I blend, maximum reductions of 75.9% NO_x, 18.2% CO, and 45.6% SO₂ were achieved, though soot increased by up to 105.2%. A soot-NO_x trade-off and engine efficiency analysis over a representative operating cycle determined that a 30% HOEF I and 20% HOEF II blends offer the most favourable balances. These blends maintain NO_x levels predominantly below 2 g/kWh and soot emissions below 0.2 g/kWh, suggesting a viable pathway for reducing the environmental impact of fishing fleets.

Keywords: e-fuels, fuel blends, emissions, marine engine, fishing vessel, real-time simulation

Nomenclature

Variables

a	Fitting coefficients (-)
A/F	Air-to-fuel ratio (kg/kg)
BMEP	Brake mean effective pressure (bar)
BSFC	Brake specific fuel consumption (g/kWh)
c	Gas concentration (%)
C	Parameter for incomplete combustion (-)
C_p	Heat capacity at constant pressure (J/kg·K)
CA50	Angle when 50% of mass is burned (°)
E	Specific activation energy (J/mol)
H	Specific enthalpy (J/kg)
k	Chemical reaction rate (kmol/cm ³ ·s·K)
LHV	Lower heating value (MJ/kg)
m	Vibe shape parameter (-)
n	Engine speed (rpm)
p	Pressure (Pa)
r	Final reaction rate (kmol/cm ³ ·s·K)
R	Gas constant (J/mol·K)
ROHR	Rate of heat release (J/deg)
S	Specific entropy (J/kg·K)
SOC	Start of combustion (°)
T	Temperature (K)
x	Mass ratio of burned fuel (-)

Greek letters

α	Crank angle
σ	Burned fuel ratio under premixed phase (-)
τ	Specific period (s)

Subscripts

act	Actual
char	Characteristic
diff	Diffusion
dur	Duration
equ	Equilibrium
fb	Fuel burned
KM	Kinetic multiplier
PPM	Postprocessing multiplier
ref	Reference
tot	Total

Abbreviations

3D	Three-dimensional
CI	Compression ignition
CII	Carbon intensity indicator
CFD	Computational fluid dynamics
CH ₂ O	Formaldehyde
CO	Carbon monoxide
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
DPF	Diesel particulate filter
EEXI	Energy efficiency existing ship index
EGR	Exhaust gas recirculation
FAME	Fatty acid methyl ester
FT	Fischer-Tropsch
GHG	Greenhouse gases
HC	Hydrocarbons
HOEF	High oxygenated e-fuel
IMCI	International Marine Certification Institute
IMO	International Maritime Organization
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LCA	Life cycle analysis
LNG	Liquefied natural gas
MDO	Marine diesel oil
MGO	Marine gas oil
NO _x	Nitrogen oxides
N ₂ O	Nitrogen oxide
OME	Oxymethylene ethers
OME ₃₋₅	Oxymethylene dimethyl ether
PN	Particle number
PM	Particulate matter
RCCI	Reactivity controlled compression ignition
RHF	Reductive olefin hydroformylation
SAE	Society of automotive engineers
SCR	Selective catalytic reduction
SO _x	Sulfur oxides
SO ₂	Sulfur dioxide
TDC	Top dead center
TTW	Tank-to-wake
WTW	Well-to-wake

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and motivation

Marine propulsion systems are still mainly based on fossil fuels, and shipping, which is responsible for approximately 90% of international trade, represents a significant source of greenhouse gases (GHG) and other pollutants. The maritime sector contributes substantial fractions of global NO_x, SO_x and CO₂ emissions, estimated at around 15% of anthropogenic NO_x and 16% of global SO_x emissions (Manchin et al. 2022; “European Maritime Safety Agency: Tackling Air Emissions”, 2025). Without the introduction of alternative fuels and exhaust gas aftertreatment systems, emissions from the maritime sector are projected to increase by 17% by 2050 (Deng and Mi 2023). In response to these trends, maritime decarbonization strategies increasingly combine regulatory, technical and operational measures aimed at reducing greenhouse gas and air pollutant emissions ("International Maritime Organization, Emission Control Areas (ECA s)", 2022; "International Maritime Organization", 2022). In parallel, fuel switching towards low- and zero-carbon alternatives is recognized as a central pathway for achieving long-term emission reduction targets within the maritime sector, in line with broader climate objectives set by the Paris Agreement and subsequent international commitments (“UNFCCC, Paris Agreement” 2016; “UNFCCC U. Glasgow Climate Pact” 2021). The fishing sector mostly comprises older vessels equipped with conventional diesel engines, which generate relatively high levels of exhaust emissions (Koričan et al. 2025). Fishing vessels operate under highly variable and cyclic load conditions, characterised by frequent speed changes, prolonged low-speed towing, and rapid transitions between operating modes. In addition, fishing vessels often spend prolonged periods near ports and coastal areas, directly affecting local air quality. In this context, the application of alternative fuels and fuel blends represents a short-term option to reduce exhaust emissions from fishing vessels while improving air quality in coastal regions.

Previous studies have shown that transient engine operation leads to higher specific NO_x emissions and altered fuel consumption patterns compared to steady-state conditions, primarily due to turbocharger lag and dynamic combustion effects (Koričan et al. 2023; Marques et al. 2019; Zare et al. 2017; Sajjad et al. 2025). Nevertheless, environmental assessments of alternative marine fuels still predominantly rely on steady-state engine data or fixed specific fuel consumption values, which can lead to systematic inaccuracies when applied to fishing vessels operating under dynamic load profiles (Perčić et al. 2023; Simonsen et al. 2018). This limitation is particularly relevant for oxygenated and dual-fuel concepts, whose combustion behaviour and emission characteristics are strongly influenced by transient operation. Consequently, realistic evaluation of emission reduction potential for fishing vessels requires cycle-based or real-time modelling approaches that explicitly account for transient engine behaviour under representative operational profiles.

1.2 Use of alternative marine fuels in dual-fuel engines

1.2.1. Commonly used alternative fuels

Different alternative fuels can be applied in the maritime sector, particularly in the context of dual-fuel engines operating on liquefied natural gas (LNG), methanol, hydrogen and

ammonia. LNG is often considered favourable from feasibility and availability perspectives, while methanol and ammonia have been investigated as potential long-term options within maritime decarbonisation pathways. The performance and environmental impacts of dual-fuel diesel/LNG engines, including the influence of operating parameters, were analysed in (J. Zhou et al. 2025), where carbon emissions were reduced by 36.4% at a diesel substitution ratio of 0.40 compared to conventional diesel operation. Measurements of exhaust emissions under steady-state and transient operating conditions for roll-on/roll-off ferries equipped with dual-fuel diesel/natural gas engines were presented in (Rochussen et al. 2023), showing that revised engine calibration and operating strategies can significantly reduce GHG emissions. From a life cycle perspective, LNG was found to reduce the carbon footprint of fishing vessels by 14-16% compared to a diesel-based propulsion system (Sjerić et al. 2025).

Methanol has also been widely investigated as an alternative marine fuel based on criteria such as sustainability, scalability and storability. A comprehensive review reported no major challenges related to methanol combustion and emissions in marine engines, while lubrication failure and corrosion remain key reliability issues (Rao et al. 2025). Parametric studies of diesel-methanol dual-fuel engines showed that the achievable substitution ratio depends on the injection strategy, with port fuel injection allowing substitution ratios of up to 50% and direct injection enabling substitution ratios of up to 95%, accompanied by NO_x reductions of up to 85% (Karvounis et al. 2025). Further reductions in NO_x emissions were achieved using methanol-water blends, although increasing water content led to reduced methanol energy fraction and increased ignition delay, requiring adjustments of injection timing to achieve favourable combustion phasing (Dierickx et al. 2023).

The hydrogen is increasingly recognized as a viable zero-carbon fuel. Extensive research on feasible production, storage and developing advance reliable consumption methods of hydrogen in internal combustion engines are ongoing. In (Gholami et al. 2022) the propulsion system of a very large crude carrier was studied, by considering the speed required for the relevant marine voyage cycle to investigate and assessed when fuel is partially switched from diesel to hydrogen. The study indicates that by changing the composition of fuels used, at the same time trying to maintain the same power output and proper performance of the engine, the amount of CO₂ emission could be reduced up to 10% when diesel is substituted by 10% of hydrogen in dual-fuel combustion mode. The optimization of diesel injection strategy to minimize unburned hydrogen in a hydrogen-diesel dual-fuel medium-speed marine engine revealed that fine tuning of injection parameters substantially lower the fraction of unburned hydrogen in exhaust gases (P. Zhou et al. 2025). From initial injection settings that resulted with 50% of unburned hydrogen, the optimized values of injection timing, spray angle and injection duration decreased unburned hydrogen to only 1% demonstrating the importance of injection strategy in effectiveness of hydrogen-diesel combustion process. The main drawback of hydrogen application in dual-fuel combustion mode is increase of NO_x emission at higher substitution ratios of diesel by hydrogen. The substitution ratio of diesel by hydrogen by 25% or higher for the same required engine power increases NO_x emissions, while reductions of soot, CO₂ and CO emissions are observed compared to diesel only operation (Sjerić et al. 2026; Awaga et al. 2024). Along with hydrogen, ammonia is also recognized as zero-carbon fuel with potential application in marine diesel engines, but the main issues in ammonia fuelled engines are high ammonia slip, high emissions of NO_x, low combustion efficiency due to low ammonia

flame speed and high ignition energy. The performance and emission characteristics from ammonia/diesel dual-fuel marine engine were presented in (Xu et al. 2023). A comparative assessment between an ammonia/diesel RCCI engine and a baseline natural gas/diesel RCCI engine, showed poor combustion efficiency with a low diesel energy share and successful operation with increased diesel usage that cut GHG emissions by 70%. NO_x emissions remain a challenge in ammonia combustion and exhaust gas aftertreatment systems need to be implemented to reduce the NO_x emissions. The effects of various injector arrangements, ignition modes, and ammonia/hydrogen blend ratios on effective combustion strategies and mitigation of nitrogen oxide (NO_x) emissions in marine engine were studied in (Sun et al. 2024). Hydrogen piloted ammonia increased engine power by 0.7% with increase of NO_x emissions by 29.4%. On the other hand, a 30% of ammonia/hydrogen blend, where ammonia and hydrogen high pressure injectors are in a close position, improves indicated power up to 3.7% and reduces unburned ammonia and hydrogen, but it significantly elevates NO_x emissions by a factor of up to 2.2. The comparisons of low and high pressure injection of ammonia in a low-speed marine engine revealed the environmental impact of both injection technology (Liu et al. 2023). The study concluded that high pressure injection currently has more potential for marine engines. Although low pressure injection offers slightly better efficiency, the high-pressure injection can provide higher power with zero fuel slip and a lower overall GHG footprint (due to lower N₂O emissions) makes it the more viable technical route for the shipping transition to carbon-free fuels. The influence of different electrode designs on ignitability of ammonia/air mixtures was experimentally analysed in (Tian et al. 2026). The researchers compared three types of electrodes and it was found that traditional tip discharge electrodes achieved the shortest initial flame development time (15.0 ms) because of its high energy density at a single point. However, it produced irregular flame morphology, which can be less reliable in practical engines. On the other hand, radiant multi-zone regulated nSDBD electrode showed excellent robustness as pressure increased. At 3 bars, it maintained stable multiple flame kernels providing the necessary balance between high-intensity active species generation and wide-range spatial control to overcome ammonia's low chemical reactivity.

Compared to dual-fuel concepts requiring multiple fuel injection systems, fuel blends that can be injected using a single injector have been widely investigated for application in conventional marine diesel engines. Oxygenated fuels such as oxymethylene ethers (OME) have demonstrated the potential to reduce both soot and NO_x emissions while maintaining high engine efficiency (Mazari Farhad 2024). Significant soot reductions were attributed to the oxygenated nature of OMEs and the absence of carbon-carbon bonds, which suppress soot precursor formation. Further studies confirmed that OME-based fuels can reduce CO and HC emissions, although higher fuel mass flow rates are required to maintain engine power output, and formaldehyde formation has been observed in the exhaust gas (Saupe and Atzler 2022).

The importance of considering fuel life cycle impacts was highlighted by a comprehensive well-to-wake assessment of marine fuels, which identified marine bio-oil as a favourable option due to low feedstock- and combustion-related emissions (Zincir and Arslanoglu 2024). Biodiesel blends containing 5-20% FAME were shown to reduce SO_x and CO₂ emissions in medium-speed marine engines without requiring significant engine modifications (Sagin et al. 2024). Experimental studies further demonstrated that compression ignition engines can operate

with higher alcohol-diesel blends of up to 30% without major hardware changes, although a slight decrease in brake power and an increase in fuel consumption were observed due to the lower heating value of the blends (Campos-Fernández et al. 2012).

1.2.2. Development of higher oxygenated e-fuels (HOEF)

Higher oxygenated e-fuels (HOEF) represent an emerging class of synthetic, carbon-neutral liquid fuels designed to combine favourable combustion characteristics with compatibility for use in existing compression-ignition engines. In contrast to conventional paraffinic e-fuels produced via Fischer-Tropsch synthesis (Panzone et al. 2020), HOEF contain oxygen atoms within their molecular structure, which enhances oxidation kinetics during combustion, reduces soot precursor formation, and enables cleaner exhaust characteristics (Dieterich et al. 2020). Two main HOEF realizations are currently under development: alcohol-based HOEF I, consisting primarily of higher aliphatic alcohols (typically C_{5–13}), and ether-based HOEF II, composed of higher aliphatic ethers (typically C_{10–22}).

A systematic development and validation of HOEF is being carried out within the E-TANDEM project (“E-TANDEM”, 2026), which aims to establish a direct, once-through power-to-liquid pathway for producing advanced oxygenated e-fuels from renewable electricity, captured CO₂ and water, Figure 1. The production concept integrates high-temperature solid-oxide co-electrolysis of CO₂ and steam to generate synthesis gas (e-syngas), followed by a hybrid tandem catalytic conversion process. In this process, olefin-selective Fischer–Tropsch synthesis is combined with reductive hydroformylation to directly yield higher alcohols (HOEF I). For the ether-based realization (HOEF II), an additional catalytic dehydration step converts higher alcohols into corresponding ethers with higher cetane numbers and improved ignition quality.

Figure 1. Overall concept proposed for a direct conversion of CO₂, water and renewable power-to-liquid higher oxygenated e-fuels.

Within the E-TANDEM project (“E-TANDEM”, 2026), surrogate formulations of alcohol-based (HOEF I) and ether-based (HOEF II) fuels were blended with Marine Gas Oil (MGO) in various volume ratios. These blends were systematically tested against the requirements of the EN 590 standard for automotive diesel fuels and the ISO 8217 specification for marine fuels. The results showed that, for alcohol-based HOEF I, most physicochemical parameters of the neat fuel and especially its blends with MGO complied with the relevant standard limits. However, the intrinsically higher hygroscopicity of higher alcohols resulted in increased uptake of atmospheric moisture, leading to water contents that do not consistently satisfy the limits

defined in EN 590. In addition, the alcohol-based HOEF I surrogate failed the copper corrosion test required by the EN 590 specification (Kremer et al. 2025). For ether-based HOEF II, both the neat fuel and its blends with MGO were found to largely fulfil the physicochemical requirements of EN 590 and ISO 8217 standards. Similar to the alcohol-based realization, elevated hygroscopicity led to increased water uptake, occasionally exceeding the permissible limits specified in EN 590. Furthermore, oxidation stability was identified as a critical parameter for HOEF II. While the addition of specific antioxidant additives effectively suppressed auto-oxidation and peroxide formation during storage periods investigated within the E-TANDEM project, this measure alone was insufficient to fully meet oxidation stability requirements, indicating the need for further optimisation through additive selection.

Overall, the development of HOEF within the E-TANDEM framework indicates the potential of higher oxygenated e-fuels produced via integrated electro- and tandem catalytic pathways for marine energy applications. The fuel formulations and blending studies provide a basis for subsequent performance and emission analyses under representative operating conditions of fishing vessel propulsion systems.

1.3 Research gap and objectives

From the literature overview, it is evident that potential of different alternative fuels and fuel blends in the decarbonization of the marine engines has been widely explored in recent years, but several significant research gaps remain, particularly in the context of fishing vessels:

- Soot-NO_x trade-offs are mostly defined based on steady state engine operations, whereas insight into soot-NO_x trade-offs under the dynamic trawler engine operation remain unknown.
- To the best of authors' knowledge, no studies have considered a real time simulation model of fishing vessel's operating cycle that adoptshighly oxygenated e-fuel-diesel blends. Specifically, there is a lack of research on blends based on two new e-fuel formulations: a mixture of synthetic aliphatic higher alcohols and a mixture of synthetic aliphatic higher ether compounds.
- Available studies on the application of alternative fuels and fuel blends in marine engines rely on the analysis of a few discrete operating points, failing to account for the dynamic engine operations typical of fishing vessels.

This study aims to address these gaps by evaluating the feasibility of highly oxygenated e-fuel-diesel blends from the perspective of engine performance and emissions. The main objectives of the study are:

- To calibrate a multiple Vibe two-zone combustion model and emission models under both steady-state operations and transient trawler fishing cycle.
- To evaluate the engine performance and emissions (CO₂, CO, NO_x, SO₂, and soot) of a marine diesel engine fuelled by different diesel substitution ratios using two new highly oxygenated e-fuels (HOEF – realization I and HOEF – realization II). This will be achieved using a real time capable simulation model at propeller curve and under the

typical trawler fishing cycle. The application of these fuel blends is intended to require minimal engine modifications for potential retrofitting.

- To define the most suitable fuel blend from the perspective of engine efficiency and the soot-NO_x trade-off in both steady-state and transient engine operation.

In our previous study (Sjerić et al. 2026) carbon-neutral and carbon-free fuels (methanol and hydrogen) were investigated under a dual-fuel combustion mode in a fishing vessel. In contrast, this study investigates e-fuel/diesel blends that are not carbon-free, but possess a higher oxygen content that directly affects the diffusion combustion and emission performance. It should be emphasized that the influence of different fuels on engine performance and emissions under transient operations can only be calculated with acceptable accuracy through a simulation model. This is because identical boundary and initial conditions can be imposed within the model, ensuring the repeatability of dynamic engine behaviour throughout the fishing vessel cycle. Conversely, evaluating this effect through on-board exhaust gas measurements is problematic; engine speed and load are never perfectly reproducible because the net drag force constantly varies depending on the catch amount, as well as wind and wave directions and intensities.

2. Methodology

2.1. Real-time simulation model

The powertrain system of fishing vessel is modelled using system simulation platform, AVL Cruise™ M, version 2021.2. AVL Cruise™ M is a multi-physics vehicle simulation and integration platform typically used in automotive engineering to model, analyse, and optimize the behaviour of entire vehicles and their subsystems. It supports conventional, hybrid, and electric powertrains and is widely used in concept development, system design, controls development, and virtual calibration procedure. Powertrain modelling capabilities of full internal combustion engine system supports the modelling of engine performance, emissions, transmission and fuel consumption analysis.

Figure 2. Simulation model of fishing vessel “Jadran 3” in AVL Cruise™ M R2021.2.

System layout of 6-cylinder marine diesel engine is shown in Figure 2. Several main structures can be identified, including the intake and exhaust systems, cylinder block, turbocharger, transmission and vessel data, operating cycle definitions, and control elements (for the start of combustion [SOC] and the fuel flow multiplier [Fuel_mlt]). The primary components of the intake system are the air cleaner, intercooler, and intake manifold, while the exhaust line consists of exhaust manifolds and plenums. Due to the unavailability of compressor and turbine operating maps, a simplified turbocharger model was used, in which the calibration of pressure ratios and the turbine discharge coefficient was performed.

The cylinder block includes six cylinders with identical architecture, each featuring an intake port, combustion chamber, direct injector, and exhaust port. The intake and exhaust ports define the valve lifts and their related flow coefficients, while the direct injector elements manage fuel injection. The core geometric data of the engine, such as the bore, stroke, and compression ratio, are defined within the combustion chamber element. Additionally, the combustion chamber configuration includes the definition of models and parameters related to heat losses, combustion, and emissions, which are described in detail in the following sections.

2.1.1. Combustion modelling

The Vibe function is often used to approximate the actual heat release characteristics of an engine. General form of Vibe function is defined as:

$$x = 1 - e^{-c \cdot \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha_{dur}} \right)^{m+1}} \quad (1)$$

where x is the mass ratio of burned fuel, C is function parameter that considers combustion efficiency, m is Vibe shape parameter and α_{dur} is duration angle of heat release. When double Vibe functions are applied, the first function is used for the modelling of premixed burning peak (uncontrolled combustion phase), while the second function describes diffusion-controlled combustion (mixing controlled phase). The ratio of fuel mass that will be burned under the premixed phase is defined by user-defined parameter σ :

$$x_1 = \sigma \cdot x = \sigma \cdot \left(1 - e^{-C \cdot \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha_{dur,1}} \right)^{m_1+1}} \right), \quad (2)$$

$$x_2 = (1 - \sigma) \cdot x = (1 - \sigma) \cdot \left(1 - e^{-C \cdot \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha_{dur,2}} \right)^{m_2+1}} \right). \quad (3)$$

Total heat release rate is finally calculated as:

$$\frac{dQ_{tot}}{d\alpha} = \frac{dx_{tot}}{d\alpha} \cdot Q_{tot} = \left(\frac{dx_1}{d\alpha} + \frac{dx_2}{d\alpha} \right) \cdot Q_{tot}, \quad (4)$$

where Q_{tot} (J) is total fuel heat input defined by lower heating value and $dx_{tot}/d\alpha$ (1/°) is normalized heat release rate defined by superposition of two Vibe function, as it is illustrated in Figure 3 (red line).

Figure 3. Application of double Vibe functions – example of superposition of normalized heat releases for start of combustion at 10°CA before TDC corresponding to engine speed of 1500 rpm.

According to marine engine manual (Cummins NT855-M series engine, (Cummins Engine Company 1979)) the static injection timing is equal to 19°CA before TDC for all operating range. Since the ignition delay cannot be captured directly by the application of Vibe function, the start of combustion was evaluated for each operating point. Experimental analysis of ignition delay, combustion performance and emissions of diesel and diesel-biodiesel blends were presented by (Shahridzuan et al. 2021). It was found that for diesel fuel the ignition delay was around 1 ms with minor influence of ambient temperature and engine load (Mustayen et al. 2022). Therefore, the ignition delay of 1 ms was used in this study. On the other hand, the parameters of two Vibe functions are defined according to experimental determination of double Vibe function parameters in diesel engine with application of biodiesel (Pešić et al. 2010). The set of selected Vibe functions parameters is listed in Figure 3. To the best of the authors' knowledge, fuel-specific ignition-delay and heat-release data for the investigated diesel/HOEF blends are not available in the literature or in the authors' experimental database; therefore, the results should be interpreted as comparative model-based trends under identical combustion-phasing assumptions. Due to different physicochemical properties of oxygenated fuels the changes in ignition delay and combustion progress are expected, but there is no reference data for the reliable evaluation of Vibe parameters modifications. The experimental results of combustion related parameters for both fuels are still not investigated. Therefore, the fixed Vibe parameters were used in this study for all considered fuel blends representing the main limitation of this study.

Based on the applied combustion model, several simplifications and limitations can be specified:

- Ignition delay and Vibe functions parameters are independent of engine speed, load and fuel blends.
- For the analysed marine engine, the static injection timing is fixed at 19°CA before TDC, and SOC - expressed in crank angles - was modified by varying the engine speed.
- The evaporation process, in terms of in-cylinder temperature decrease, is neglected.
- Detailed chemical reactions were not calculated; instead, air-fuel mixtures are defined by a classic species approach where the thermodynamic properties of the fuel and air are approximated by polynomial functions.
- Due to internal mixture preparation, a hydrocarbon (HC) emission sub model is not available.
- The effect of external EGR is not simulated because the analysed marine engine does utilize an EGR system.

The application of Vibe functions and two-zone modelling approach enabled the real-time simulation of the trawler fishing cycle. Bearing in mind that net hauling process of considered trawler can last up to 5 hours, the real-time capability of the simulation model represents a significant benefit compared to other engine and combustion simulation tools.

2.1.2. Emission modelling

The NO_x formation model implemented in AVL Cruise™ M is based on (Pattas and Haefner 1973). The following 6 reactions, that are based on the well-known Zeldovich mechanism, are considered and specified in Table 1.

Table 1. Reactions and coefficients considered for the overall NO_x emission.

	Stoichiometry	Reaction rate $k_i = k_{0,i} \cdot T^a \cdot e^{\left(\frac{-T_{A_i}}{T}\right)}$	$k_0 \left[\frac{mol}{cm^3 \cdot s \cdot K} \right]$	$a [-]$	$T_A [K]$
R1	<chem>N2 + O = NO + N</chem>	$r_1 = k_1 \cdot c_{N_2} \cdot c_O$	$4.93 \cdot 10^{13}$	0.0472	38048.01
R2	<chem>O2 + N = NO + O</chem>	$r_2 = k_2 \cdot c_{O_2} \cdot c_N$	$1.48 \cdot 10^8$	1.5	2859.01
R3	<chem>N + OH = NO + H</chem>	$r_3 = k_3 \cdot c_{OH} \cdot c_N$	$4.22 \cdot 10^{13}$	0	0
R4	<chem>N2O + O = NO + NO</chem>	$r_4 = k_4 \cdot c_{N_2O} \cdot c_O$	$4.58 \cdot 10^{13}$	0	12130.6
R5	<chem>O2 + N2 = N2O + O</chem>	$r_5 = k_5 \cdot c_{O_2} \cdot c_{N_2}$	$2.25 \cdot 10^{10}$	0.825	50569.7
R6	<chem>OH + N2 = N2O + H</chem>	$r_6 = k_6 \cdot c_{OH} \cdot c_{N_2}$	$9.14 \cdot 10^7$	1.148	36190.66

The concentration of N₂O is calculated according to the following equation:

$$c_{N_2O} = 1.1802 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot T^{0.6125} \cdot e^{\left(\frac{9471.6}{T}\right)} \cdot c_{N_2} \cdot \sqrt{p_{O_2}}, \quad (5)$$

where c_{N_2O} is concentration of nitrous oxide, T is local combustion temperature (in two zone model it is temperature of the burned zone), c_{N_2} is nitrogen concentration and p_{O_2} is partial pressure of oxygen in the gas phase.

The final rate of NO production/destruction is calculated as follows:

$$r_{NO} = C_{PPM} \cdot C_{KM} \cdot 2 \cdot (1 - \alpha^2) \cdot \frac{r_1}{1 + \alpha \cdot AK_2} \cdot \frac{r_4}{1 + AK_4}, \quad (6)$$

where:

$$\alpha = \frac{c_{NO,act}}{c_{NO,equ}} \cdot \frac{1}{C_{PPM}}, \quad AK_2 = \frac{r_1}{r_2 + r_3} \quad \text{and} \quad AK_4 = \frac{r_4}{r_5 + r_6} \quad (7)$$

The constant C_{PPM} (-) represents the post-processing multiplier, while C_{KM} (-) is NO_x kinetic multiplier for tuning the calculated exhaust gas emission level.

The CO formation model is based on the model proposed by (Onorati et al. 2001). The following two reactions are considered, as specified in Table 2.

Table 2. Reactions and coefficients considered for CO emission.

	Stoichiometry	Reaction rate
R ₁	$CO + OH = CO_2 + H$	$r_1 = 6.76 \cdot 10^{10} \cdot e^{\left(\frac{T}{1102}\right)} \cdot c_{CO} \cdot c_{OH}$
R ₂	$CO + O_2 = CO_2 + O$	$r_2 = 2.51 \cdot 10^{12} \cdot e^{\left(\frac{-24055}{T}\right)} \cdot c_{CO} \cdot c_{O_2}$

The final rate of CO production/destruction r_{CO} is calculated as:

$$r_{CO} = C_{Const} \cdot (r_1 + r_2) \cdot (1 - \alpha), \quad (8)$$

where C_{Const} is tuning parameter to scale the rate of CO formation, r_1 and r_2 are reaction rates of CO formation and α is fraction of the actual CO concentration to its equilibrium concentration calculated as:

$$\alpha = \frac{c_{CO,act}}{c_{CO,equ}}, \quad (9)$$

where $c_{CO,act}$ and $c_{CO,equ}$ are current and equilibrium CO concentration, respectively.

The soot emissions model considers the formation and oxidation mechanism (Schubiger et al. 2002). The soot formation reaction is related to the diffusion combustion rate, while the oxidation mechanism depends on the actual soot mass and available oxygen in the burned zone.

A soot formation reaction is related to the combustion rate of diffusion combustion $\frac{dm_{fb,diff}}{dt}$:

$$\frac{dm_{soot,f}}{dt} = A_{S,f} \cdot \frac{dm_{fb,diff}}{dt} \cdot \left(\frac{p}{p_{ref}}\right)^{n_1} \cdot e^{\frac{E_{s,f}}{R_m T}} \quad (10)$$

where $A_{S,f}$ (-) is soot formation tuning parameter, p (Pa) is actual in-cylinder pressure, p_{ref} (Pa) is reference pressure, $E_{s,f}$ (J/mol) is activation energy for soot formation. The soot oxidation reaction depends on the actual soot mass in the cylinder and available oxygen in the burned zone:

$$\frac{dm_{soot,o}}{dt} = A_{s,o} \cdot \frac{1}{\tau_{char}} \cdot m_{soot}^{n_2} \cdot \left(\frac{p_{o2}}{p_{o2,ref}} \right)^{n_3} \cdot e^{\frac{E_{s,o}}{R_m T}} \quad (11)$$

where $A_{s,o}$ (–) is soot oxidation tuning parameter, τ_{char} (s) is characteristic mixing time related to overall heat release rate, m_{soot} (kg) is actual soot mass, p_{o2} (Pa) is partial pressure of oxygen, $p_{o2,ref}$ (Pa) is reference partial pressure of oxygen, $E_{s,o}$ (J/mol) is activation energy for soot oxidation. In both equations (10) and (11) R_m (J/kgK) and T (K) are individual gas constant and temperature of burned zone, respectively. In addition, n_1 , n_2 , n_3 (–) are fixed model constants.

CO₂ and SO₂ emissions are calculated using a known carbon and sulphur mass ratio in the fuel and the stoichiometric equation of the carbon and sulphur oxidation process:

Equation (12) indicates that burning of 1 kg of carbon will produce 44/12 kg of carbon dioxide, while burning of 1 kg of sulphur will produce 2 kg of sulphur dioxide (see Eq. 13). Specific CO₂ and SO₂ emissions are calculated using the following equations:

$$CO_2 \left[\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{kWh}} \right] = \frac{44}{12} \cdot \text{BSFC} \left[\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{kWh}} \right] \cdot \text{Carbon mass ratio} [-], \quad (14)$$

$$SO_2 \left[\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{kWh}} \right] = 2 \cdot \text{BSFC} \left[\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{kWh}} \right] \cdot \text{Sulfur mass ratio} [-], \quad (15)$$

where BSFC represents brake specific fuel consumptions of diesel and fuel blends calculated by the application of real time simulation model in this study.

2.2. Modelling and properties of diesel, higher oxygenated e-fuels and fuel blends

The basic physicochemical characterization of both e-fuels was conducted, and the resulting analytical data are reported in Table 3, alongside the diesel fuel properties prescribed by EN 590 standard. HOEF realization I is a mixture of synthetic aliphatic higher (C₅₋₁₃) alcohols, where more than 50% of the mass consists of pentanol, hexanol and heptanol. HOEF realization I can be obtained by blending specific pure alcohol compounds - most of which are commercially available - in weight proportions that resemble the alcohol distribution produced by the tandem e-syngas conversion process. HOEF realization II is a mixture of synthetic aliphatic higher (C₁₀₋₂₂) ethers where more than 50% of mass consists of undecanol, dodecanol, and tridecanol. For the preparation of HOEF II, the mixture of synthetic aliphatic higher

alcohols must be converted into their corresponding ether derivatives. This is attained through the catalytic, bimolecular dehydration of alcohols which, next to producing ether compounds, releases water as a side-product.

Table 3. Overview of diesel and e-fuels properties.

Fuel name	Diesel	HOEF realization I (higher alcohols)	HOEF realization II (higher ethers)
Label	D	HOEF I	HOEF II
Composition	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ – C ₁₅ H ₂₈ : 75.0 % (vol.) C ₆ H ₆ + C ₈ H ₈ : 25.0 % (vol.)	C ₅ H ₁₁ OH: 19.8% (wt) C ₆ H ₁₃ OH: 17.5% (wt) C ₇ H ₁₅ OH: 15.1% (wt) C ₈ H ₁₇ OH: 12.8% (wt) C ₉ H ₁₉ OH: 10.7% (wt) C ₁₀ H ₂₁ OH: 8.8% (wt) C ₁₁ H ₂₃ OH: 7.1% (wt) C ₁₂ H ₂₅ OH: 5.8% (wt) C ₁₃ H ₂₇ OH: 2.4% (wt)	C ₁₀ H ₂₂ O: 5.0% (wt) C ₁₁ H ₂₄ O: 11.0% (wt) C ₁₂ H ₂₆ O: 26.1% (wt) C ₁₃ H ₂₈ O: 16.1% (wt) C ₁₄ H ₃₀ O: 16.1% (wt) C ₁₅ H ₃₂ O: 11.0% (wt) C ₁₆ H ₃₄ O: 7.0% (wt) C ₁₇ H ₃₆ O: 3.0% (wt) C ₁₈ H ₃₈ O: 2.0% (wt) C ₁₉ H ₄₀ O: 1.0% (wt) C ₂₀ H ₄₂ O: 0.8% (wt) C ₂₁ H ₄₄ O: 0.5% (wt) C ₂₂ H ₄₆ O: 0.3% (wt)
Density at 15°C (kg/m ³)	830	826	787
Kinematic viscosity at 40°C (mm ² /s)	2.00 - 4.50 (EN 590)	4.20	1.38
Oxygen mass ratio (%)	0	13.44	7.96
Carbon mass ratio (%)	86.25	72.78	78.04
Max. sulphur content (mg/kg)	10 (EN 590)	0	0
Water content (mg/kg)	200 (EN 590)	386	804
Stoichiometric air to fuel ratio (kg/kg)	14.70	17.44	18.44
Lower heating value (MJ/kg)	42.8	36.2	38.7

In the real-time simulation model, the fuel properties are described as a function of the instantaneous in-cylinder temperature. The specific heat capacity at constant pressure C_p , specific enthalpy H^0 and specific entropy S^0 are calculated using the following polynomial functions:

$$\frac{C_p}{R} = a_1 + a_2 \cdot T + a_3 \cdot T^2 + a_4 \cdot T^3 + a_5 \cdot T^4, \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{H^0}{RT} = a_1 + \frac{a_2}{2} \cdot T + \frac{a_3}{3} \cdot T^2 + \frac{a_4}{4} \cdot T^3 + \frac{a_5}{5} \cdot T^4 + \frac{a_6}{T}, \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{S^0}{R} = a_1 \cdot \ln T + a_2 \cdot T + \frac{a_3}{2} \cdot T^2 + \frac{a_4}{3} \cdot T^3 + \frac{a_5}{4} \cdot T^4 + a_7, \quad (18)$$

where T is temperature, while $a_1 - a_7$ are fitting coefficients defined according to Chemkin thermodynamic database (Kee et al. 1993). There is set of 7 coefficients valid for temperature below temperature validity range (set to 1000 K), while the other set of coefficients is applied for higher temperatures. Since the polynomial coefficients are unknown for newly defined e-fuels, the existing polynomial coefficients of diesel fuel were used in this study. Other fuel properties, such as molar mass, stoichiometric A/F ratio, carbon mass ratio and oxygen mass ratio are calculated according to hydrogen, carbon and oxygen numbers defined by fuel composition specification given in Table 3. New fuel thermodynamic data files are generated for both e-fuels using gas property generator available within AVL Cruise™ M installation. Afterwards the fuel data files are assigned to the workspace of simulation model and corresponding mass fractions of diesel and e-fuels are specified to model the fuel blends, as listed in Table 4.

Table 4. Overview of analysed e-fuel/diesel blends.

Label of fuel blend	D-HOEF I 70-30%	D-HOEF I: 50-50%	D-HOEF II: 90-10%	D-HOEF II: 80-20%
Diesel volume ratio	70%	50%	90%	80%
HOEF volume ratio	30%	50%	10%	20%
Diesel mass ratio	70.10%	50.12%	90.47%	80.84%
HOEF mass ratio	29.90%	49.88%	9.53%	19.16%
Carbon mass ratio	82.22%	79.53%	85.47%	84.68%

Within E-TANDEM project four diesel-HOEF blends were tested (given in Table 4) on the basic physicochemical properties and therefore the presented study followed the volume ratios defined within the performed physicochemical analysis. It was found at higher volume ratios of both e-fuels that the corrosion effect, lubrication and hygroscopicity properties do not fulfil EN 590 norm. It was also concluded that observed negative effects could be improved with specific additives that could improve fuel blend characteristics. Hence, the higher substitutions

of diesel fuel with HOEF (above 50% for HOEF I and above 30% for HOEF II) were not analysed in the presented study.

The Croatian fishing vessels operating in the Adriatic Sea use a fuel commonly referred to as „blue diesel“. This fuel is intended for specific sectors (agriculture, forestry, fisheries) due to its lower excise duties; however, it is also used for ships and shares the same quality as standard diesel defined by the EN 590 standard. Therefore, this study analyses diesel fuel blended with the two previously described formulations: the alcohol-based fuel (HOEF I) and the ether-based fuel (HOEF II).

3. Results and discussion

Result section presents the calibration of the real-time simulation model under both steady-state engine operations and the dynamic engine operations typical of a trawler fishing cycle, followed by the detailed simulation results of e-fuel/diesel blends. The engine performance and emissions characteristics from the application of the e-fuel/diesel blends are compared to baseline operation with neat diesel, which represents the existing state of the trawler propulsion system.

3.1. Calibration of real time simulation model

In this study, the same marine engine and trawler “Jadran 3” operating in the Adriatic Sea are used, as already described in our previous study (Sjerić et al. 2026). The vessel is propelled by a Cummins NT855-M300 four-stroke diesel engine. The inline, six-cylinder engine features a water-cooled design, complemented by a turbocharger and intercooler system. It delivers a peak brake power of 224 kW at engine speed of 1800 rpm. Furthermore, the propulsion unit is compliant with IMO Tier II standards regarding NO_x emission limits. More details and specifications about measuring equipment for vessel speed and fuel consumption installed on the fishing vessel can be found in (Sjerić et al. 2026).

The simulation model, which incorporates a double Vibe function, was calibrated based on fuel consumption data under full load conditions and at several operating points along a typical propeller curve. The NO_x emission sub-model was calibrated at full load at the nominal engine speed to ensure that the calculated NO_x emissions do not exceed the IMO Tier II limit. Meanwhile, the soot model was calibrated along the propeller curve, where specific soot emissions are higher than those at full load.

The simulation results are divided into two parts: the first evaluates steady-state engine operating conditions corresponding to the propeller curve, while the second includes the simulation of transient engine operation during the fishing vessel’s net-towing period, where the propeller load is imposed into simulation model. Assuming that the propeller curve defined by the engine manufacturer aligns with the characteristics of the actual propeller used on the selected fishing vessel, it is possible to determine the average engine speed that corresponds to the average fuel consumption measured on-board. The transient engine operation was simulated by replicating a typical net-towing cycle, during which the measured vessel speed and propeller torque curve were introduced as input data into the simulation model; the cumulative fuel consumption at the end of the transient cycle was then compared to the measured data.

Following this validation, each steady-state operating point along the propeller curve and the transient cycle were analysed under the application of different e-fuel/diesel blends.

3.1.1. Steady state engine operation

The maximum engine brake power and the power required for a typical propeller are plotted and compared in Figure 4a, while the volumetric fuel consumption rates are compared in Figure 4b. The reference performance data of the Cummins NT855-M300 engine are defined according to ISO 8665 and SAE J1228 reference conditions, as well as the IMCI procedure for rating marine engine power. The prescribed reference conditions include an ambient air pressure of 1 bar, an air temperature of 25°C, and a relative air humidity of 30%. The baseline fuel consumption is calculated based on a fuel temperature of 16°C, a LHV of 42.78 MJ/kg and a fuel density of 838.9 kg/m³.

Figure 4. Calibration of steady state engine operation for a) brake power and b) fuel consumption at full load and typical propeller curve.

Full and partial engine loads corresponding to the propeller curve were simulated with six different engine speeds in steps of 200 rpm, with one additional engine speed of 1500 rpm where the maximum brake torque occurs. Each operating point was simulated over a period of 30 seconds to achieve a converged solution.

The first calibration step included the adaptation of air excess ratio (λ) at full load conditions. Since the analysed marine engine has direct fuel injection system, the minimum air excess ratio was set to 1.35 at full load. Due to unavailability of turbocharger performance maps, the operation of turbocharger was simulated with the simplified model where at full load conditions the turbine layout calculation was applied, while the simulation of propeller curve included the boost pressure calculation mode of turbocharger. At full load conditions the desired compressor pressure ratio will be achieved with the calculation of turbine discharge coefficient at each engine speed. The average value of turbine discharge coefficient equal to 0.25 is then imposed into the boost pressure calculation mode for the simulation of propeller curve and for the transient engine operation. The maximum pressure ratio set at full load condition was equal to 1.4 at engine speed of 1500 rpm when the maximum brake torque of 1251 Nm is achieved that is 1.01% higher compared to reference). The propeller curve was simulated by increasing the excess air ratio to values when engine brake power is equal to reference curve, as plotted in Figure 3a. The volume fuel consumption for each operating point is defined in postprocessing step using the calculated fuel mass flow from AVL Cruise™ M and reference fuel density equal to 838.9 kg/m³. For the modelling of mechanical losses in the engine caused by the friction (bearings, camshaft) and by the required power of fuel injection pump and oil pump, Shayler-Leong-Murphy model was applied (Shayler et al. 2003). Fine calibration of fuel consumption was made with tuning of engine friction multiplier that was set to 1.5. The increase of friction multiplier is reasonable due to fact that applied friction model does not directly calculate the work required by water pump and electric generator. Since the simulation results show good agreement with reference ones, especially at propeller curve, it is expected that engine performance under dynamical operation will be correctly captured as well.

3.1.2. Transient engine operation - typical trawler fishing cycle

The dynamical engine behaviour was analysed under a typical trawler fishing cycle whose velocity is plotted in Figure 5. Over a period of 99 minutes, the trawler continuously pulls the net at an average speed of approximately 5 km/h, where the drag slightly increases over the time due to the accumulating catch. The measured velocity profile of the fishing vessel was imposed into real-time simulation model to represent the target velocity of the simulation.

Figure 5. Comparison of measured and simulated fishing vessel speed over transient cycle.

In our previous study (Sjerić et al. 2026), the drag coefficient was introduced into of AVL Boost™ cycle simulation model to capture the effect of net drag on cumulative fuel consumption. In the present study, the imposed propeller torque curve was defined using a mechanical consumer element (see Figure 2) connected to the crankshaft. The propeller torque is calculated by dividing the propeller power, shown in Figure 4a, by the crankshaft’s angular velocity. With this configuration in the simulation model, a higher vessel speed will require an increased engine speed and load in accordance with the propeller curve.

The installed monitoring system on the vessel includes the volume flow device DFM Marine 1000CCAN TA which measure volume fuel consumption by tracking the difference between fuel supply to the engine and return flow to the tank. During the measurement of trawler fuel consumption, diesel fuel temperature was measured, and it was equal to 46°C. According to EN 590, density of diesel fuel is equal to 830 kg/m³ at temperature of 15°C. Diesel fuel density decreases as temperature increases; hence at temperature of 46°C diesel fuel density drops to 813 kg/m³ according to corrections defined under Petroleum Measurement Standards (“Manual of Petroleum Measurement Standards” 2004). The calculated fuel mass flow in the simulation model was integrated over the time and divided with previously corrected diesel fuel density resulting with the cumulative volume fuel consumption plotted in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Comparison of measured and simulated cumulative fuel consumption of diesel fuel for transient cycle.

During the first 11 minutes, the simulation results matched the measured fuel data well, followed by a small discrepancy that occurred around the 12th minute of the trawler cycle. This deviation was caused by a peak in the fishing vessel's velocity, which reached 7 km/h. At that moment, the engine load should temporarily increase, resulting in a higher amount of injected fuel in the cylinders to achieve the higher engine speed. During the final 15 minutes of the trawler cycle, the measured data indicate a more intensive fuel consumption, which was obviously caused by a drag increase that was not directly captured by the simulation model. This discrepancy is partially compensated by the overprediction of fuel consumption around the 12th minute, resulting in a final cumulative fuel consumption that is 2.6% lower than the measured result.

An analysis of engine speed distribution was performed using the simulation results along the propeller curve, and the percentage of engine speed occurrence is plotted in Figure 7. The histogram was constructed using an engine speed step size of 50 rpm. The shape of engine speed histogram plotted in Figure 7 closely resembles a normal distribution with a clearly pronounced averaged speed. Under the analysed trawler cycle, the engine operates at a speed of 1350 rpm for 72% of time. The presence of lower and higher engine speeds in the histogram is caused by the variation of vessel speed below and above the average value of 5 km/h. Additionally, the averaged engine speed could be calculated by considering the averaged fuel consumption from the measurements and applying a linear interpolation to the propeller data provided in Figure 4b. Averaging the volumetric fuel flow from the measured data shown in Figure 6 yields 29.3 L/h. The linear interpolation of fuel consumptions along the propeller curve in Figure 4b results in average speed of 1358 rpm, thereby confirming the dominant engine speed observed in the histogram.

Figure 7. Histogram of engine speeds for trawler operating cycle.

From the presented calibration results of trawler velocity, fuel consumption, and engine speed distribution of the original diesel propulsion system, it can be concluded that the simulation model is well-prepared and sufficiently detailed for the application of various fuel blends across both steady-state and dynamic engine operations. The average real-time factor during transient engine operation - defined as the ratio between computational time and the trawler cycle duration- was equal to 0.965, thereby confirming the real-time capability of the applied simulation model.

3.2. Simulation results of e-fuel/diesel blends

Once the simulation model was calibrated in terms of engine performance prediction and before the application of different fuel blends, the calibration of emission sub models was required. The calibration of emission sub models was performed over steady state engine operations at full load and propeller curve, considering declared emission standard of marine engine. Calibration results of emissions are described later, and they were plotted together with emissions related to the application of different fuel blends. The NO_x and soot sub-models were not validated against fuel-specific experimental data for the investigated diesel/HOEF blends. Therefore, full predictive accuracy of absolute emission values cannot be claimed. However, since all blends were evaluated using the same model structure, boundary conditions and operating cycle, the results are interpreted as comparative emission trends rather than fully validated absolute predictions.

3.2.1. Engine performance and emissions at steady state operations

The comparison of the calculated BSFC for neat diesel and the four different fuel blends along the propeller curve is plotted in Figure 8. The lowest BSFC is achieved with the application of neat diesel, whereas the application of all fuel blends increases BSFC depending on the substitution ratio. This increase in BSFC is caused by the presence of oxygen within e-fuels, which results in a lower LHV, as listed in Table 3.

In this study, the amount of injected fuel per cylinder was adjusted for each fuel blend to maintain the exact engine power required by the propeller, while all other simulation parameters were kept constant. A minimum BSFC increase of 0.97% is observed with the application of the fuel blend where diesel is replaced by 10% (by vol.) of the synthetic aliphatic higher ether mixture (HOEF II). Conversely, the maximum BSFC increase reaches 8.89% when 50% of the diesel volume is substituted by the mixture of synthetic aliphatic higher alcohols (HOEF I).

Figure 8. Brake specific fuel consumption for neat diesel and different fuel blends calculated for 7 operating points at propeller curve.

Various experimental studies on the application of different fuel blends in CI engines are primarily based on engine performance and emission analyses conducted without adjusting the engine injection parameters; hence, a slight change in brake power or torque is typically observed. For example, adding 10%, 15%, 25%, and 30% of three different oxygenated fuels (diethylene glycol, di-n-butyl ether, and tripropylene-glycol monomethyl ether) to conventional diesel fuel revealed increases of 0.25% to 7.5% in BSFC, depending on the oxygen content within the fuel (Nabi et al. 2024). Similarly, an experimental study incorporating the addition of up to 20% (by vol.) isobutanol into conventional diesel fuel also confirmed an increase in BSFC compared to neat diesel operation (Karabektas and Hosoz 2009). The average increases in BSFC compared to pure diesel fuel ranged between 2.06% and 8.55% for 5% and 20% of isobutanol additions, respectively.

According to IMO Tier II level and for nominal engine speed of 1800 rpm (when maximum engine power occurs) the threshold of specific NO_x emission is equal to 7.85 g/kWh. The adoption of NO_x kinetic multiplier C_{KM} (see Equation 6) from default value of 0.64 to 0.19 resulted with simulated level of the maximum specific NO_x emission equal to 7.75 g/kWh at engine speed of 1500 rpm corresponding to the location of maximum brake torque. Under these

operating conditions, the maximum boost pressure was observed with peak in-cylinder temperatures of 2146.4 K. Results of specific NO_x emissions calculated at full load and along the propeller curve are plotted and compared in Figure 9. The full load simulation over the engine speeds was performed to calibrate the NO_x sub model, while the propeller curve results with different fuel blends are important because the operating points under transient engine operation will be located on the propeller curve. As the substitution of diesel with e-fuel is getting higher, the NO_x emission reduces due to reduction of peak in-cylinder temperatures. The average reduction in NO_x emission, when diesel is replaced by mixture of synthetic aliphatic higher ether compounds (HOEF II) with 10% (vol.), is equal to 22.87%. The maximum reduction of NO_x emission along the propeller curve in the presented study was observed when 50% of diesel volume is substituted by a mixture of synthetic aliphatic higher alcohols (HOEF I) and it is equal to 78.72%. The peak in-cylinder temperatures were reduced by 1.6% (for D-HOEF II: 90-10%) and 7.7% (for D-HOEF I: 50-50%) compared to neat diesel operation. It is evident from results shown in Figure 9 that application of diesel substituted by 30% or more with aliphatic higher alcohols (HOEF I) will enable engine operation along the propeller curve under Tier III limit.

Figure 9. Specific NO_x emissions for neat diesel and different fuel blends calculated for full engine load and 7 operating points at propeller curve.

In general, NO_x emissions from a diesel engine depend on various parameters, such as fuel properties and engine operating conditions. Higher combustion temperatures and oxygen concentrations in the cylinder contribute to elevated NO_x emissions. Alcohols usually produce lower combustion temperature due to their lower heating value compared to diesel. An experimental study of fuel blends with up to 20% of isobutanol added to conventional diesel revealed a maximum NO_x reduction of 20% at 1800 rpm under full-load conditions (Karabektas and Hosoz 2009). It was observed that the reduction in combustion temperature, the extension of the ignition delay, and the low LHV exert a combined effect that diminishes NO_x emissions

when using alcohol/diesel blends. Conversely,, the presence of oxygen in fuel blends can promote the oxidation process, resulting in slightly increased peak values for the ROHR (Nabi et al. 2024). Variations in ignition delay were not simulated in the presented study because the Vibe function cannot predict ignition delay, however, its effect on the start of combustion can be manually imposed on the model. Similarly, details of the oxidation process were not captured because chemical kinetics modeling was not employed. Given that the parameters of double Vibe functions were fixed, the observed NO_x decreases are influenced solely by the reduced LHV of the applied fuel blends. Comparatively, the study presented by (Jayabal et al. 2022) confirmed that a methyl ester/diesel blend at 50% by volume combined with 20% of EGR can decrease NO_x emissions by 61.91% compared to neat diesel operation. Furthermore, the effects of adding different proportions (2.5%, 5%, and 7.5%) of diethyl ether to corn oil-derived biodiesel fuel were investigated by(Ergen 2024). It was determined that a 5% diethyl ether-biodiesel blend combined with 10% EGR provides the best balance of performance and nitrogen oxide emissions, leading to a NO decrease of up to 70% compared to standard diesel fuel.

Specific soot emissions from the full load with neat diesel and along the propeller curve with neat diesel and fuel blends are shown in Figure 10. While NO_x model was calibrated at full load conditions, the soot emission model required the calibration at low load and low engine speed where the maximum specific soot emissions were observed.

Figure 10. Specific soot emissions for neat diesel and different fuel blends calculated for full engine load and 7 operating points at propeller curve.

The soot formation tuning parameter $A_{s,f}$ (-) was modified from the default value of 1000 to 2300 so that the maximum specific soot emission at propeller curve is close to Tier II limit equal to 0.2 g/kWh. The maximum soot emission of 0.182 g/kWh occurred at propeller curve and at engine speed of 1000 rpm. Soot emissions in marine diesel engines are inversely related

to engine load along the propeller curve. The relationship between soot emissions and propeller curve is primarily governed by the air-fuel mixture quality and combustion efficiency. At low load and engine speed the boosting pressure is lower, resulting with lower in-cylinder flow and weak air-fuel mixing that reduces local excess air ratio (λ). This leads to incomplete combustion increasing the rate of soot formation in the range of low load and low engine speed. In the applied simulation model this effect is captured by the reduced in-cylinder temperature at low load operations leading to pronounced soot formation.

The fuel composition and properties, such as density and kinematic viscosity, play the most important role in the soot emissions. The examination of the effect of diesel fuel density, viscosity, and compressibility factor on the fuel injection system, engine combustion characteristics and emissions was performed in (Zannis et al. 2007). The experimental results confirmed that increased diesel fuel viscosity by 75% contributed to the increased soot emissions up to 20% at low engine load. The analysis of emissions from auxiliary marine 6-cylinder engine fuelled by different ratios of diesel and biodiesel (from B0 to B100) revealed the maximum increase of PN emissions occurred for B100 cases that are 300% higher at 25% of load compared to neat diesel operation (Yang et al. 2022). Details about the composition of PM emitted, indicated that it includes large amounts of organic carbon (30-40%) and elemental carbon (10-20%), which are key components of soot. Due to high viscosity of biodiesel at injection pressures up to 350 bar the addition of 50% of biodiesel to conventional diesel increased the smoke opacity by 25% (Wu et al. 2022).

From the simulation results in this study, the addition of e-fuels to diesel increases soot emissions for all operating points over the propeller curve, as it can be seen from Figure 10. For more detailed analysis of effects contributing to increased soot emissions, the comparisons of several in-cylinder properties for different fuel blends are plotted in Figure 11 for steady state operating point at 800 rpm.

Figure 11. Comparisons of partial oxygen pressure (a), total in-cylinder temperature (b), combustion air excess ratio (c) and soot mass (d) for steady state engine operation at 800 rpm and at propeller curve.

Due to reduced lower heating values of diesel-HOEF blends compared to neat diesel, the increased fuel mass injection was applied to maintain the same engine power required by propeller. Under such conditions the air excess ratio (λ) is reduced (Figure 11c) which decreases partial oxygen pressure (Figure 11a) and according to Equation 11 the rate of soot oxidation is reduced. On the other hand, the rate of soot formation calculated with Equation 10 depends on in-cylinder pressure and temperature. With slightly reduced in-cylinder temperatures (Figure 11b) the soot formation is increased leading to the final soot mass at the end of combustion process higher than soot mass achieved with the neat diesel combustion. This effect is present for other operating points at propeller curve.

HOEF I consists mainly of higher alcohols and has a higher oxygen mass fraction and lower heating value than HOEF II, which consists mainly of higher ethers. Therefore, for the same engine power, HOEF I requires a higher injected fuel mass, leading to a stronger reduction in air excess ratio, partial oxygen pressure and in-cylinder temperature. This results in a more pronounced NO_x reduction, but also reduces soot oxidation and increases the calculated soot emissions.

In contrast, HOEF II has a higher heating value and lower oxygen content, causing milder changes in temperature, air excess ratio and emission formation. Consequently, HOEF II shows a smaller NO_x reduction, but also a lower soot penalty.

The average soot emission increase of 16.94% over the propeller curve is achieved when diesel is replaced by mixture of synthetic aliphatic higher ether compounds (HOEF II) with 10% (vol.). When diesel is substituted by a mixture of synthetic aliphatic higher alcohols (HOEF I) with 50% (vol.), the average soot increase over propeller is equal to 237%. Despite that, the most of operating points at propeller curve are still below Tier II limit equal to 0.2 g/kWh.

3.2.2. Soot-NO_x trade-off from steady state and transient operation

Beside fuel properties, there are a lot of engine operating parameters influencing the soot-NO_x emissions from CI engines. The optimization of intake and fuel injection parameters in a heavy-duty CI engine fuelled with e-diesel and oxymethylene dimethyl ether blend led to average reductions of 28% less in NO_x with additional decreases in CO, HC, and soot levels (García et al. 2025). In the presented study, the engine operating parameters with application of fuel blends were not optimized, representing the potential to further decrease exhaust gas emissions, especially with EGR application. Results of soot-NO_x emissions from the operating points at propeller for neat diesel and fuel blends are plotted in Figure 12 representing typical soot-NO_x trade-off diagram. Figure 12 also includes trendlines that were added to create better graphical representation of e-fuel effects. The additions of both e-fuels significantly suppress NO_x emission, while soot emission is increased although both e-fuels contain oxygen. On the other hand, smaller LHV reduced peak in-cylinder temperatures, while the decrease of air excess ratio (λ) was required to maintain the same engine power contributing to elevation of soot emission. This effect is more pronounced at maximum engine speed of 1800 rpm when D-HOEF I blends were applied. From soot-NO_x trade-off diagram shown in Figure 12 that is related to steady state operation, it can be concluded that almost all fuel blends will satisfy Tier II soot level and Tier III NO_x level with minor steady state operating points exceeding those levels.

Figure 12. Soot-NO_x trade-off relationship at propeller curve for diesel and different fuel blends.

Under dynamic conditions of trawler cycle the engine is constantly exposed to the variation of load. During such transient operations, a temporary disequilibrium between the engine torque and air supply (turbocharger lag) occurs. Such condition results in a momentarily lower A/F ratio, causing a sudden overshoot of soot emissions compared to steady state operation. Therefore, soot-NO_x trade-offs from the transient engine operation for neat diesel and different fuel blends are plotted in Figure 13. While the averaged result over transient cycle (yellow circle markers) indicates that engine operation at propeller curve satisfies Tier III for NO_x and Tier II for soot, dispersion of operating points gives more insight into soot-NO_x emissions. Both variants of D-HOEF II blends (see Figure 13d and Figure 13e) mostly satisfy Tier II soot level, while certain number of operating points exceed Tier III NO_x level. On the other hand, D-HOEF I blends (see Figure 13b and Figure 13c) mostly satisfy Tier III NO_x level, but certain number of operating points are above Tier II soot limit. In the context of compromise choice between the minimum soot and NO_x emissions, fuel blend where 30% of diesel is replaced with a mixture of synthetic aliphatic higher alcohols (Figure 13b) represents the most suitable fuel for the application in trawler engine.

Figure 13. Soot-NO_x trade-off relationships over transient engine operation for diesel and different fuel blends.

3.2.3. Engine performance and emissions from transient operation

Results for specific emissions of NO_x and soot, the overall engine efficiency, peak in-cylinder temperature and air excess ratio as averaged results over transient engine operation are plotted in Figure 14. Reduction of NO_x emissions, visible from Figure 14a, is caused with reduced in-cylinder temperature (Figure 14c) and reduced partial oxygen pressure that, according to Equation 5, decreases concentration of N₂O. Reduced N₂O concentration influences to the reduced production of NO. This effect is more pronounced as the diesel is blended with higher volume ratios of HOEF. On the other hand, the soot emissions have opposite trend and it elevates with higher volume ratios of HOEF, as already discussed under Figure 11.

Figure 14. Engine performance and emissions over transient operation for different fuel blends – time averaged results.

A slight decrease in overall engine efficiency plotted in Figure 14b can be observed with the addition of HOEF to diesel fuel. It is attributed to the fuel flow regulator that controls the fuel mass flow during the transient engine operation to satisfy desired fishing vessel speed. As already mentioned, the engine management was performed with increased fuel mass injection when diesel-HOEF blends are considered which decreases averaged air excess ratio from 2.04 to 1.72, as it can be seen in Figure 14c. On the other hand, the average engine power over transient operation is reduced from 100.77 kW for neat diesel to 100.76 kW for D-HOEF I:50-50% blend contributing to minor decrease of overall efficiency. Applied parameters of double Vibe functions were fixed in this study for all fuel blends, although the modification of injection timing and start of combustion potentially could improve the overall efficiency. In addition, different thermodynamic properties of air-fuel mixture and different lower heating values of HOEF decreases peak in-cylinder temperatures (Figure 14c) and partial oxygen pressure. Therefore, the emissions of NO_x decreased while soot emissions increased when diesel-HOEF blends are applied. The most suitable substitutions of diesel fuel with HOEF from the analysed fuel blends from the perspective of soot-NO_x emissions and trade-off, and overall engine efficiency deterioration correspond to D-HOEF II: 80-20% and D-HOEF I:70-30% fuel blends.

3.3. Discussion

The changes of CO₂, CO, NO_x, SO₂ and soot emissions were evaluated by averaging emission results over the typical trawler operating cycle that lasts 99 minutes. Changes are referenced to emissions of neat diesel combustion, and they are plotted in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Changes of emissions for CO₂, CO, NO_x, SO₂ and soot for diesel-HOEF blends – averaged results over transient engine operation (changes are referenced to neat diesel operation).

CO₂ emissions are defined considering stoichiometric equation of carbon oxidation (see Equation 14) and using the calculated BSFC values plotted in Figure 8. Even though applied e-fuels have lower carbon mass ratio compared to conventional diesel, emissions of CO₂ are slightly increased, where the maximum change from transient operation is equal to +0.32%. Potential adaptation of engine operating parameters (e.g., injection start) could improve brake thermal efficiency, where CO₂ emissions could reach the same levels that are achieved with neat diesel operation. It is already well known from the literature that TTW emissions of CO₂ from different e-fuels combustion do not reflect the real potential in the decarbonization if WTW and LCA are not performed (Zincir and Arslanoglu 2024).

Carbon oxide emission model was calibrated so that the maximum specific CO emissions at full load conditions when the engine is fuelled with neat diesel do not exceed 5 g/kWh, as prescribed by Tier II for marine engines with displacement per cylinder above 1.2 dm³ and below 2.5 dm³. CO emission reductions were observed over all fuel blends with the maximum reduction of 18.2% for D-HOEF I:50-50% blend. CO emission drop is obviously encouraged with the oxygen content inside fuel blends which surpassed the effect of reduced in-cylinder temperatures. Changes in CO emissions are in line with findings from the literature (Sagin et al. 2023; García et al. 2025; Saupe and Atzler 2022) where similar fuel blends were analysed.

Changes of NO_x emissions are already discussed on the propeller curve results for steady state operation shown in Figure 9. The overview of NO_x emission changes over the transient engine operation leads to identical conclusions already given for steady state operating points. When diesel is replaced by mixture of synthetic aliphatic higher ether compounds (HOEF II) with 10% (vol.) NO_x emissions are reduced by 22.1%. The maximum NO_x reduction is achieved when diesel is substituted by a mixture of synthetic aliphatic higher alcohols (HOEF I) with 50% (vol.) is equal to 75.9%. The observed NO_x reductions are primary influenced by decrease of in-cylinder temperatures and decrease of partial oxygen pressure that is reduced due to decrease of air excess ratio. Trends in NO_x emissions are in line with findings from the literature (Nabi et al. 2024; Karabektas and Hosoz 2009; Jayabal et al. 2022; Ergen 2024). It should be emphasized that applied simulation model does not include detailed modelling of combustion oxidation process which is usually promoted by the presence of oxygen content in the fuel contributing to more complete combustion and increase of ROHR. Hence the quantified NO_x reductions in this study are potentially overestimated, but it should be checked once the experimental results of fuel blends combustion will be available.

SO₂ emissions are defined considering stoichiometric equation of sulphur oxidation (see Equation 15) and using the calculated BSFC values plotted in Figure 8. Calculation of SO₂ emissions assumes that diesel fuel has maximum sulphur content of 10 ppm (according to EN 590 standard), while considered e-fuels are sulphur-free. As the substitution ratio of diesel fuel is getting higher, the reduction of SO₂ emissions is higher. The maximum SO₂ reduction of 45.6% was observed when diesel is substituted by a mixture of synthetic aliphatic higher alcohols (HOEF I) with 50% (vol.).

Reduction of in-cylinder temperatures and mixture enrichment that reduced partial oxygen pressure increased soot emission for all fuel blends. Literature review (Zannis et al. 2007; Yang

et al. 2022; Wu et al. 2022) indicates that soot emissions are mostly increased at low load conditions and low injection pressures when different diesel fuel blends were applied. The soot emission increase in this study ranges from 10.3% up to 105.2%, as it can be seen from Figure 15. According to soot-NO_x trade-off from transient engine operation and overall engine efficiency drop plotted in Figure 14b it can be adopted that diesel fuel blended by 30% (vol.) of HOEF I and by 20% (vol.) of HOEF II represent compromised solution to satisfy Tier III level of NO_x (< 2 g/kWh) while maintaining soot emissions mostly below Tier II level (< 0.2 g/kWh) and maintaining the engine operation without significant drop of overall efficiency. Under such conditions, trawler propulsion system will reduce CO, NO_x and SO₂ emissions in ranges 6.0%-10.8%, 39.9%-56.5% and 18.4%-26.4%, respectively. For CO₂ and soot emissions adverse effects are observed where the average increase of 0.13%-0.18% for CO₂ and 25.4%-46.6% for soot are achieved.

4. Conclusions

The real-time simulation model of the original trawler propulsion system was developed in AVL Cruise™ M. The model was calibrated across a set of steady-state operating points and validated against measured data for vessel velocity and fuel consumption during a trawler net-hauling period in the Adriatic Sea. Two new e-fuel formulations – HOEF I, based on the mixture of synthetic aliphatic higher alcohols, and HOEF II, based on a mixture of synthetic aliphatic higher ether compounds, were defined, and their corresponding blends with diesel fuel were integrated into the simulation model. Simulations were performed along the propeller curve and throughout a typical trawler net-hauling period using four distinct fuel blends (D-HOEF I: 70-30%, D-HOEF I: 50-50%, D-HOEF II: 90-10% and D-HOEF II: 80-20%). The resulting engine performance and emissions characteristics were then compared to baseline operation with neat diesel. Based on this research, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The simulation of several steady state operating points covering the entire propeller curve, combined with the linear interpolation of results for the average engine speed, reproduces the global engine performance and emissions typical of a various trawler operations.
- The simulation of transient engine operation reflects more realistic characteristics of engine raw emissions, especially regarding the soot-NO_x trade-off.
- The lower heating value of HOEF are lower than that of diesel. Therefore, to maintain the same engine power, an increased fuel blend mass flow was required. Consequently, the brake specific fuel consumption increases, accompanied by a minor increase in CO₂ emissions. A maximum CO₂ increase of 0.32% occurs when diesel is blended with 50% by volume of HOEF I (higher alcohols). Correcting the injected fuel mass is much easier to implement in a potential marine engine retrofitting scenario rather than elevating the intake boost pressure to maintain identical engine power.
- The application of both formulations of HOEF (higher alcohols and high ethers) reduces CO emissions by up to 18.2% due to the presence of oxygen inside both e-fuels.
- The maximum reduction of NO_x emission of 75.9% is realized with diesel fuel blended with 50% of volume with HOEF I. Reduction of NO_x emission is caused by the mixture enrichment that reduces partial oxygen pressure and peak in-cylinder temperatures.

- Volume substitution of diesel fuel with 30% (or higher) of HOEF I and with 20% of HOEF II decreases NO_x emissions below Tier III level for the analysed marine engine and trawler operating cycle enabling the potential operation under the emission control areas (ECA). Under the application of such fuel blends the engine overall efficiency will be maintained close to the operation with neat diesel.
- The calculation of changes in SO₂ emissions is based on the brake specific fuel consumption, under the assumption that the diesel fuel has a maximum sulphur content of 10 ppm as defined by EN 590 standard. A maximum reduction in SO₂ emissions of 45.6% is achieved when diesel fuel is blended with 50% by volume of HOEF I.
- The analysed fuel blends increased specific soot emissions due to mixture enrichment, which lowered the partial oxygen pressure and in-cylinder temperatures. Although the maximum soot increase reaches 105.2% when diesel is blended with 50% HOEF I, most of the operating points along the propeller curve lie below the Tier II limit of 0.2 g/kWh.
- Based on the analysed soot-NO_x trade-off relationships and overall engine efficiency during transient engine operations, diesel fuel blended with 30% (by vol.) of HOEF I and 20% (by vol.) of HOEF II represents a balanced compromise. These formulations satisfy the Tier III level for NO_x (< 2 g/kWh) while maintaining soot emissions mostly below the Tier II level (< 0.2 g/kWh) and preserving engine operation without a significant drop in overall efficiency. With these specific fuel blends, CO and SO₂ emissions are reduced by 6.0%-10.8% and 18.4%-26.4%, respectively.

Further development of the model may include the introduction of fuel dependent combustion parameters, such as variable ignition delay and Vibe parameters depending on the operating point, enabling a more detailed assessment of the influence of the physicochemical properties of HOEF fuels on combustion and emission formation. Fuel dependent combustion and emission parameters could be investigated in the future work with the application of three-dimensional CFD simulation model giving the insight into visualization of combustion process and spatial distributions of different components such as NO_x, CO, soot and SO₂. Based on the achieved combustion progresses for different fuel blends the ignition delay and double Vibe function parameters can be calculated. In addition, future work could investigate calibration and system-level measures to mitigate increased soot formation under transient operation, including turbocharger control optimisation, variable boost strategies, or the application of EGR concepts tailored to oxygenated e-fuels. Finally, the analysis may be extended to a broader range of HOEF formulations and blending ratios and coupled with vessel-level operational strategies, aiming to achieve a more favourable trade-off between fuel consumption and emissions during dynamic fishing operations such as net hauling.

CrediT authorship contribution statement

Momir Sjerić: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ivana Jovanović:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Nikola Vladimir:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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